

INTERRELATIONSHIP OF SOCIAL SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION

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Annotation: In spite of the fact that the achievements of science have entered our lives within the framework of the socialization of education, the conditions created by the state in the field of science, despite the opportunities, among young people, there is an increase in diseases such as mass frivolity, meaningless life, Internet addiction, pretentiousness, "popularity syndrome" obtaining it requires raising the social outlook in the society, changing the views on life, and reevaluating the criteria for happiness.

Key words: education, dialectic, development, society, socialization

– With the serious aggravation of socio-economic and political-cultural problems in the international arena, heated debates and discussions about the realization of future hopes and dreams regarding the fire of war, civil war, especially religious extremism and terrorism, bioterrorism, and human rights and freedoms are escalating [1]. At the same time, it was recognized that the achievements of humanity in the field of science and technology pose a threat to modern civilization. In a word, in the rapid development of social development, the activation of the religious factor is observed due to the ideas about its base (cyclical). In this sense, the stability of social development, important solutions of international and regional security, proposals and initiatives of the government of Uzbekistan regarding "Enlightenment and religious tolerance" are being scientifically analyzed by the scientists of our republic [2]. In scientific studies, scientists have recognized the harmful aspects of social development for humans, that not all changes are good, and that they lead to different consequences in different cultures [3].

– The role of mass education is more clearly manifested by the conformity of political leaders and leaders to the historically formed views on the development of society, the dreams and wishes of mankind. For this reason, together with the necessity of education, it is necessary to form its mass, to promote and promote the fact that young people should be enlightened in order to create their destiny with their own hands based on national interests. After all, social development requires deep knowledge for young people to take conscious and purposeful active action. In Uzbekistan, the Strategy of Actions forms education as a social institution universally inclusive and educates the creative thinking skills of young people who have mastered the national centuries-old spiritual heritage: scientific knowledge and professional skills. "Consequently, we need to increase our attention to human capital," the President of Uzbekistan says, "for this we must mobilize all the possibilities" [4]. We believe that the rational use of the energy and initiative of young people will further expand the possibilities of social development, especially spiritual revival in Uzbekistan.

– It was determined that the research of this problem in the social sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out in a number of priority directions:

– - due to the implementation of the concept of "National Development and Education" under the priority of the "Social Development and Education" programs adopted by the world community, high indicators are being achieved in the general literacy of the population;

– - the interrelationship of education in the development of society is recognized in foreign European countries as a legal protection of human rights and freedom, against socio-cultural discrimination;

- The essence of the state policy on youth in Uzbekistan, the compulsory primary education, the liberalization of all areas of education, the direct concern of the President of Uzbekistan to create all the conditions for education for young people are explained in harmony with the future prospects of our country - the third Renaissance of education and upbringing.

The Republic of Uzbekistan expressed its support for the UN Millennium Summit on Human Development on the basis of partnership. In this sense, it is emphasized that social development and education are related and development indicators are to ensure a comfortable and quality life for people [5]. These indicators and criteria are an expression of the universal and national dialectic of social development and education in our country.

The goal of the new stage of society's development is to create a socio-economic and cultural environment for every citizen to fully demonstrate his potential in healthy living conditions. In this sense, in the report of the Government of Uzbekistan on Human Development at the UN, "Education is directly related to the level of health and life expectancy of the population, that is, an important indicator of human development. "Educated population takes care of their health, applies preventive measures well, lives mainly according to a healthy lifestyle, diagnoses the disease in time, provides first aid, and applies for qualified medical services"[6].

President of Uzbekistan Sh. M. According to Mirziyoyev's principle, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest heritage is good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance", relying on the national spiritual heritage to achieve social development, the idea of young people mastering modern knowledge and becoming truly enlightened and highly cultured is our idea. scientific programming of our research. In particular, the declaration of Uzbekistan as "Country of the Year" in 2019 confirms the social value of education in the ongoing creative reforms [7].

Tarjima turlari

Matn tarjimasi

Avtomatik aniqlash

O'zbek

Rus

Ingliz

Ingliz

Rus

O'zbek

Manba matn

Жамиятнинг ривожланишида шахснинг ижтимоийлашуви, таянч ва таркибий ҳиссиётда рационал дунёқарашни маърифий тадбир ва тарбиянинг объектив ва субъектив омиллари инсон ҳаётига бевосита таъсир этади. Ижтимоий тараққиёт ва

таълим диалектикасида инсон ўзига хос индикатор вазифасини ўтайди. Шу боис, таълим ижтимоий тараққиётнинг муҳим омили вазифасини ўташи билан бирга ижтимоий тараққиётнинг глобал жараёни илғор педагогик технологиялар жараёнига дунё халқларини тортади.

Ижтимоий тараққиёт жамиятда яшаш қулайликларини, ахборотнинг айланиш тезлигини оширади, имкониятларнинг беқиёс даражада ўсишига олиб келади. Чунки ахборот оқими ижтимоий тараққиёт билан бевосита боғлиқ ҳолда инсон билим ва дунёқарашини белгилаб беради. Соҳа бўйича мутахассис олимлар замонавий ахборот технологияларининг тараққиёти туфайли ёшлар орасида интернет қарамлиги туфайли кунлик вақт бюджетининг асосий қисми интернет маълумотлари билан боғлиқ эканлигини таъкидлаб ўтишган[8]. Айтиш мумкин таълим тараққиёти ва бозор иқтисодиёти муносабатлари диалектикасида ахлоқий маърифатнинг роли жиддий ортиб бориши туфайли тадқиқотчилар ўта мураккаб ижтимоий ҳодиса, деган хулосага ҳам келганлар[9].

Ижтимоий тараққиёт ва таълим уйғунлиги шароитида олий таълимнинг халқ хўжалиги ишлаб чиқаришининг таркибий қисмига айланиши билан таълим ва тарбия омили миллий тараққиёт концепциясига боғлиқ фаолият мезони қилиб олинди[10].

Мустақиллик тажрибаси жамият тараққиётида таълимнинг моддий-техника базасини яратиш орқали амалга оширилиши муносабати билан 2011 йилда етти мингдан ортиқ мактаб ва академик лицейларнинг бинолари янгидан қурилиб ёки таъмирланиб, ўқувчиларнинг билим олиши учун юксак сифатли таълим муҳити ташкил этилди. Бу ҳол таълим тизимида хорижий инвестиция ва хусусий сектор иштирокини тажриба сифатида жалб қилиш, давлат-хусусий шериклик ва нодавлат таълим муассасаларини ҳам таълим ва тарбия соҳасига жалб этишга олиб келди. Натижада, “давлат-хусусий шериклик асосида барпо этилаётган хусусий мактабгача таълим масканлари сўнгги 2019 йилда икки баробар кўпайиб 568 тани ташкил этди. Яна мингта шундай боғча очиш бўйича амалий ишлар бошланди”[11].

Таълимнинг жаҳон ижтимоий тараққиётига диалектик алоқадорлиги юзасидан тадқиқотчиларнинг фикрларида, умумий бўлса-да, ижобий ёндашув мавжуд, яъни улар “...ёшлар билан узвий боғлиқ ҳолда мамлакатни барқарор ривожлантириш ғояси заминида билимли ва ақл заковотли етук авлодни улғайтириш тарбияси ётади. Зеро, ўқимишли, билимли, ақлзаковотли, руҳан бардам ва жисмонан бақувват ёшларгина истиқлол ва тараққиёт йўлини босиб ўта олади, мамлакатни барқарор ривожлантиришга эришади. Ота боболаримиз қадимдан бебаҳо бойлик бўлмиш илм маърифат, таълим ва тарбияни инсон камолоти ва миллат равнақининг энг асосий шarti”, дея таъкидлайдилар[12]

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Tafsilotlar bilan tanishish

2 763 / 5 000

Tarjima natijalari

Tarjimasi

In the development of the society, the objective and subjective factors of the socialization of the individual, the rational worldview in the basic and structural sense, the educational event and the education have a direct impact on the human life. In the dialectic of social development and education, man acts as a unique indicator. Therefore, while education is an important factor of social development, the global process of social development attracts the peoples of the world to the process of advanced pedagogical technologies.

Social development increases the comfort of living in society, the speed of information circulation, leads to an incomparable increase in opportunities. Because the flow of information determines human knowledge and outlook in direct connection with social development. Experts in the field have noted that the main part of the daily time budget is related to Internet information due to the Internet addiction among young people due to the

development of modern information technologies [8]. At the same time, due to the significant increase in the role of moral enlightenment in the dialectic of educational development and market economy, researchers have come to the conclusion that it is a very complex social phenomenon [9].

In the conditions of social development and educational harmony, with higher education becoming a component of national economy production, the factor of education and upbringing was taken as a criterion of activity related to the concept of national development[10].

In 2011, more than seven thousand schools and academic lyceums were newly built or renovated, and a high-quality educational environment was created for students to learn. This situation led to the involvement of foreign investment and private sector participation in the education system as an experiment, public-private partnership and non-governmental educational institutions in the field of education and training. As a result, "private preschools built on the basis of public-private partnership doubled in 2019 and amounted to 568. Practical work on opening a thousand more such kindergartens has begun" [11].

Regarding the dialectical relationship of education to world social development, there is a positive approach in the opinions of the researchers, although it is general, that is, they say that "...the education of raising an educated and intelligent mature generation lies on the basis of the idea of sustainable development of the country in integral connection with the youth. After all, only educated, knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally strong and physically strong young people can walk the path of independence and development, achieve sustainable development of the country. Our forefathers emphasized that knowledge, which is a priceless wealth since ancient times, education and training is the most important condition for human perfection and the development of the nation.[12]

In this sense, the 35th place of Uzbekistan in the "Global Index of Innovations" by the international business school "Inssad" represents the relevance of education in the development of society.

In the sense of quality and effectiveness of education in the social development of Uzbekistan, it was envisaged to bring the professional quality of higher education to the level of world standards. In order to increase the quality of higher education and develop the country's economy at a steady pace, highly qualified engineer personnel in accordance with the requirements of the modern digital economy renewed the activity in the labor market of the higher education institution. At the same time, the conflict between education and development: the irreconcilable conflict between cultures, religions, and regions, which is put on the agenda even on the principle of "two rams' heads do not boil in one pot", is a cause of concern for the scientific community.

Currently, a historical period has begun, in which fundamental reforms are taking place in various spheres of society, and paradigmatic updates are taking place in the field of science and knowledge. The main indicator of the level of social development in society is the personal activity of a person, that is, the formation of a perfect person based on the preparation of young people for a complex and increasingly improving social life, and the solution of his social and economic tasks has become a priority. It should be noted that the process of social development in society is irregular. It has been confirmed that the process of social change, shift and development is characterized by irregularity.

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